

DELIVERABLE D7.7
Report on Workshop 1

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CONTENTS

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1.1 Description of the deliverable content and objectives	4
1.2 Deviation from objectives, corrective action	4
1.3 Summary of the workshop results	5
1.4 Planned and executed dissemination activities	6
2 WORKSHOP DESCRIPTION	7
2.1 Introduction	7
2.2 Group work: target markets	8
2.3 Gallery of the pilots	14
2.4 Plenary work: supply chains	14
2.5 Retrospective discussions about the project	16
3 CONCLUSION	18
4 APPENDIX.....	19

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 Description of the deliverable content and objectives

The need for secondary materials has increased over the years as a result of the global shift towards circular economy practices and sustainability. Secondary raw materials are derived from the recycling of waste and are crucial to reducing the environmental impacts of exploiting the earth's finite natural resources. To this end, the EU funded ICARUS project is aimed, among others, at retrieving 95% of high-value secondary raw materials from wastes obtained from silicon ingot and wafer manufacturing. The multifaceted nature of environmental problems and implementation of possible solutions require the participation of stakeholders. For the purpose of creating a transparent and flexible atmosphere for the exchange of diverse values, insights, feedbacks, and knowledge about the ICARUS project, an online stakeholder workshop was organised by bifa on October 17, 2024 from 9:00 AM to 12:00 PM. This stakeholder workshop, on Secondary Materials SM1 also aimed to raise awareness among the key stakeholders of the ICARUS project and generate inputs on the target markets for secondary silicon (Si), graphite, silica, and hydrogen as well as the project's supply chain. This report highlights the content and outcomes of the stakeholder workshop on Secondary Materials.

Bifa organised and moderated the workshop, with support from the project partner Benkei. Benkei also assisted with organizing and marketing the workshop. In addition, the project partners SINTEF and Chemconserve supported the workshop with their expertise and both gave presentations. Each of the four pilot plants in the project also presented posters of their main contributions to the ICARUS project during the workshop. Several experts from the consortium and external stakeholders, especially from academia, registered for and participated in the workshop. Specifically, 29 of the 53 registrations for the workshop were external participants. However, 28 participants attended the workshop, including 4 external stakeholders.

The online workshop was successfully conducted with the aid of Zoom and Miro tools. Presentations and plenary work, as well as group work in small groups through break-out rooms were carried out on the Zoom platform. Additionally, the canvas tool Miro was used as a complementary tool for visualisation and in conjunction with individual and group brainwriting. Several methods were employed to develop the format and facilitate the workshop. In particular, analyses and discussions were conducted using a SWOT analysis and a supply chain check-up. A "hot air balloon retrospective" was also planned.

1.2 Deviation from objectives, corrective action

Although the workshop was originally scheduled for June 12, 2024, it was postponed after the planning team and the project coordinator agreed on a later date after the summer holidays in Germany, as most interested parties could not meet on that day. The communication strategy developed by bifa and Benkei can be summarized as follows:

- Social Media Campaign: a total of 7 dedicated posts were shared on LinkedIn (see Figure 1). The aim was to reach people unaware of the project's activities but looking for information on the topics. Project partners were asked to forward and share the social media posts.

- Multiple emails were sent to the consortium reminding them to share the information about the workshop with their network to reach interested stakeholders.
- A flyer (Figure 2) was designed and distributed at the 41st edition of the EU-PVSEC exhibition, held in Vienna, Austria in September 2024.
- Information were posted on the project’s website as well as event-posts on the ICARUS and bifa websites.

Figure 2: Social media post

Figure 1: The workshop flyer

1.3 Summary of the workshop results

This ICARUS workshop was focused on the target markets for the secondary raw materials silicon, graphite, silica and hydrogen in addition to obtaining information about the opportunities and challenges within the supply chain of the project.

This report summarizes the opinions and conclusions made by the participants. The following statements can be summarised:

Target markets of the secondary raw materials

1. **Silica** can be easily recovered as a waste product and almost in the same purity as the original product. However, high purification costs and low availability affects its recovery as a secondary material.
2. **Hydrogen** is a substance with high energy content and is expected to be in high demand in the future, but it is hard to store and transport and its recovery results in high costs for ATEX and technology switch.
3. **Silicon** has high availability of material and technology to recycle the products (requirements of recycling), however there is not enough virgin material available, end-users and recycling volume are currently limited.

The supply chain of the project:

1. Material supply issues

European waste products differ in quality compared to those from China, mainly due to different impurity levels. To address this, a systematic comparison of sources, suppliers, impurity levels and metal content is essential.

2. Production challenges

The European photovoltaic (PV) value chain is currently not strong enough. Relocating production to the US, re-exporting at competitive prices or identifying new target markets would be possible mitigation measures.

Experimental production of metallurgical grade silicon (MG-Si) is based on three materials: Si-Kerf, silica and graphite. While silica and quartz crucible silica are effective for MG-Si production via carbothermic reduction, high-density graphite proves unsuitable due to low reactivity. Purification efforts, including briquetting, are partially effective for Si kerf and silica, but not for graphite.

3. Use of recycled materials in high end applications

A clear branding strategy is required for recycled silicon as the project will produce three products with different levels of purity. Each product will need to emphasize unique selling points such as environmental benefits (improved LCA) and ethical labels (e.g. 'slave-free'). In addition, market integration of new materials takes about 10 years, which could be accelerated by selling the process or product directly to target regions such as the US.

1.4 Planned and executed dissemination activities

A short summary of the workshop was published on the ICARUS website and also posted on social media (see *Figure 3*). Moreover, participants will receive this public deliverable.

Our workshop took place last week as expected. Participants were able to discuss with the consortium about the supply chain and potential markets. Group discussions allowed to exchanged about target markets for silica, hydrogen and silicon. A SWOT analysis was then performed on the capacity to reach markets. Finally, the supply was presented, and the discussion covered its current and potential challenges. In the meantime, posters presenting the 4 project pilots were discussed in details by the respective responsables (ROSI, ReSiTec AS, LuxChemtech GmbH and NOSI). More details to come in a few weeks with a long summary and details!

Figure 3: Social media post about the workshop

2 WORKSHOP DESCRIPTION

The workshop was divided into five main activities. These included the introduction, group work on the topic of “target markets”, presentation of gallery of the pilots, plenary discussion on the topic “supply chains” and plenary retrospective discussions about the project. The detailed agenda can be found in the appendix.

2.1 Introduction

The workshop commenced with an introduction by Roksana Rotter (bifa), who welcomed the participants, explained the objectives of the workshop and presented the agenda. This was followed by an insightful presentation by the project leader, Martin Bellmann (Sintef), who gave a general overview of the project. His presentation focused on secondary raw materials, the value chain, the work of the project’s pilots and also the challenges the project is currently tackling.

Next, Marco Pieterse (Chemconserve) gave a presentation on the target markets of secondary raw materials relevant to this project. He specifically focused on silicon, graphite, silica, and hydrogen, highlighting their characteristics, price developments and challenges of placing these materials on the global market. This was followed by an introduction to the Miro online tool, which was necessary for the group work that followed (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Introduction to Miro

2.2 Group work: target markets

The group work took place in three groups within breakout sessions. Participants were able to join the group they were most interested in. Each group worked on the topic of target markets, focusing on different secondary materials:

Group 1: Silica

Group 2: Hydrogen

Group 3: Silicon

The moderators from bifa (Ruth Berkmüller, Monika Bokelmann and Roksana Rotter) explained the tasks and coordinated the group work. Each group completed three steps, which are presented in the following:

Step 1: Voting

The first task for the participants was to vote on the potential markets for the secondary raw materials: silicon, graphite, silica, and hydrogen. The participants had a choice of up to 21 target markets and could in principle vote for as many as they wished, with the caveat that no single market could receive more than one vote from any participant. The results from the voting of Group 3 are presented in Figure 5.

Step 1

Figure 5: Voting results for Group 3

A total of 16 participants took part in the voting. By combining the voting results of the three groups, the combined results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Combined voting results of the three groups

Votes out of 16	Market
14	Metallurgy (steelmaking, crucibles, ladles, furnace linings, moulds, ...)
13	Photovoltaic Industry (photovoltaic cells, ...)
10	Battery Industry (lithium-ion batteries, other battery technologies, ...)
9	Chemical Industry (sealants, adhesives, lubricants, glass, ceramics, filler material, catalysts, ...)
8	Semiconductor Industry (integrated circuits, microprocessors, memory chips, insulating materials, ...)
8	Transportation (fuel cells, ...)
8	Construction Industry (concrete additives, cement, glass, ...)
7	Energy and Heating Industry (oil and gas recovery, (hydrogen) fuel cells, energy storage...)
7	Industrial Applications (automation, power electronics, abrasives, filtration, ceramics, ...)
5	Automotive Industry (electronics, electric vehicles, tire manufacturing, rubber compounds, ...)
5	Paints and Coatings (fillers and extenders, anti-corrosion coatings, ...)
4	Electronic Industry (devices, home appliances, heat management, ...)
4	Agriculture (soil amendment, pesticides, ammonia, ...)
3	Aerospace and Defence (navigation systems, communication systems, thermal management, composite materials,...)
3	Research and Development (graphite, nanotechnology, ...)
2	Consumer Products (pencils, sporting goods, ...)
2	Healthcare Industry (imaging equipment, wearable health monitors, ...)
2	Pharmaceuticals and Cosmetic Industry (excipients, toothpaste, antiperspirants, ...)
1	Food Industry (anti-caking agent, beer clarification, ...)
1	Telecommunications (networking equipment, 5G technology, ...)
1	Nuclear Industry (neutron moderator, structural material, ...)

Step 2: Specification markets

After the voting results were presented to the participants, the groups brainstormed about missing target markets that should be added to the list. Thereafter, the group engaged in a lively discussion regarding the potential markets with a view to targeting appropriate technologies, products, and even companies possibly in need of secondary raw materials. The findings of the group's brainstorming and potential markets' discussions are presented below.

Group 1:

- German company RW Silicium: Coarse Silica for production of mg-Silicon in arc furnace
- Wacker, Elkem, DOW: Silicon, Silica

Group 2:

- Heating companies
- Heavy duty vehicles

Group 3:

- Silicon Nitride
- Aluminium foundries: AlSi alloys for the automotive industry
- Silicon: Solar grade and semiconductor grade through TCS production
- Silicon: Silicon anodes in batteries
- Battery industry: inclusion of recycled content in raw materials
- Targeting higher end markets with next generation silicon cathode/anode after graphite

Step 3: SWOT analysis

The next step was the evaluation of the secondary raw material's (group 1: silica/group 2: hydrogen/group 3: silicon) chances of success in the relevant target markets using SWOT analysis. The SWOT analysis is a framework used in strategic planning to assess a company's competitive position in the marketplace. The analysis looks at four key characteristics (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) that are typically used to compare how competitive the company can be within its industry. It considers both internal (strengths and weaknesses) and external (opportunities and threats: market environment) factors. A well-conducted SWOT analysis provides a factual basis for informed decision-making and can stimulate innovative concepts for new products or strategic initiatives. *Figure 6* demonstrates the results of the SWOT analysis of group 2.

Hydrogen: reaching target markets

Figure 6: SWOT analysis of Group 2

The outcomes of the SWOT analyses of the three groups are presented in the tables *Table 2*, *Table 3*, and, *Table 4*.

Table 2: Outcome of the SWOT analysis from Group 1

Group 1: Secondary Silica	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be easily recovered as a waste product • High purity close to virgin silica (quartz) material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting the needed purity levels • Availability of too small volumes (trend to pull several ingots from one silica/quartz melt container) • Origin of waste source (China)
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High potential to replace virgin/primary silica/quartz • Securing raw material supply • CO2-Emission reduction • Expected quartz shortage in the future if PV production continues to grow at the same pace 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High purification costs • Disrupted PV supply chain in Europe

Table 3: Outcome of the SWOT from Group 2

Group 2: Secondary Hydrogen H ₂)	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In Icarus it is a byproduct • Shift from traditional energy-producing countries • Fossil -> solar • Breaking up monopolies • High future demand expected • Energy storage • It has a high energy content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sufficient energy available for all applications (electrification) • Availability of energy • Additional costs for ATEX • The current cost of production is relatively high compared to other fuels • Hard to store and transport • Setting the political framework
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology change in raw iron production from basic oxygen furnace (BOF) to direct reduced iron (DRI) • Slow down climate change • Potential for green H₂ label? • Strong rising demand expected with limited availability • It is a good storage for electricity, especially renewables • Substitution of natural gas for heating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alternative H₂ sources are being developed. H₂ to become a commodity. Does ICARUS H₂ scale meet potential price targets? • Requirements for purity might not be reached in ICARUS • High ATEX cost • High cost of technology switch • It is easily flammable, hence its safety is a critical topic of discussion

Table 4: Outcome of the SWOT analysis from Group 3

Group 3: Secondary Silicon	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of the materials for the production of huge quantities • Availability of the technology to recycle the products • Non-slave labour origin • Environmental benefit • Increased resilience of the supply chain in EU (multiple sources) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unknown raw material • Incipient production • Limited successful introduction stories • Niche Market Penetration (Currently Limited End-Uses) • Lack of trust • Cost effectiveness • Has been considered a waste material - not always good procedures on handling of these materials • Need to define standards + branding (Weakness that need to be converted into a strength) • Lot of risks that the company will not come into the "recycled game" if they don't have a success story as an example • Explosive nature of the material – environment, health and safety (EHS) concerns
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Silicon is a critical material • Possibility to fine-tune the recovery process • Increase in availability • Need to find a name for the recycled kerf (Re-Silicon? / Green Silicon? / Re-Si?) • Increased market demand (PV and semiconductor market growth) • Meet the requirements for low carbon footprint materials • Supply chain resilience • The recovery is a necessity, since mining is not enough to meet the market needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding of recycled materials as lower quality materials • Competition from virgin silicon: dominance of established supply chains and price volatility • Recycling infrastructure challenges: limited recycling volume capacity and lack of robust collection systems

2.3 Gallery of the pilots

The next item on the workshop's agenda was the presentation of the project's pilots' gallery. Four breakout rooms were prepared and named according to the pilots: ROSI, RESITEC, LUXChemtech, and NORTHERN SILICON. Each of the pilot companies prepared a poster about their tasks in the ICARUS project and presented it during the breakout sessions. Participants were able to move freely between the breakout rooms, interact with the pilots and ask questions. The posters can be found in the appendix.

2.4 Plenary work: supply chains

The link to the next Miro board was shared with the plenary, showing the supply chain of the project. Thereafter, Martin Bellmann introduced the supply chain. The plenary was then given the task of looking at the supply chain and putting a tick if it works well or a thunder if there are challenges/potential challenges within the supply chain. If they put a thunder, they also had to put a pink sticky note next to it and explain what the thunder stands for. The next step was a conversation in which the pink sticky notes were explained by the participants and possible approaches to solving these challenges/potential challenges were discussed. These approaches were captured on green sticky notes. Figure 7 is a screenshot of the commented supply chain.

Figure 7: ICARUS Supply chain showing participants' comments

The outcomes of the plenary discussion are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Outcome of the plenary discussion

Challenge/ potential challenge	Approaches to solve the challenge/potential challenge
Question: How are the waste products comparable to waste products from manufacturers in China?	Comparison between the impurity level from different sources → Comparison of the sources, impurity levels, suppliers and variation in the metal content
EU market is rapidly changing (availability of material)	Manage the materials from supplier to supplier
Si-waste-to-material (pilot D): can be extended to other Si waste products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Si waste streams can be beneficial for Pilot D • More open for waste sources other than Kerf → Interest for EoL modules / Additional waste streams • Si-kerf and silica pot scrap works well for producing of MG-Si by carbothermic reduction
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The European customer PV value chain has shut down: No kerf anymore in Europe, everything comes from China. Kerf is a waste. It requires a lot of money to get waste stream back to Europe. • China is building recycling kerf plants. Other Asian countries can also give access to kerf. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ReSiTec is looking for crucible. • NOSI needs to identify market and customers looking for 6N quality → Niche markets in the chemistry industry ? • Re-export it with a competitive price • NOSI could move to the US • NOSI can purify the material. Working fine at NorSun.
Three input materials needed for metallurgical grade Si at good purity. Does not work for Graphite because graphite has too low reactivity	Briquetting solution working for Kerf and Silica but not graphite.
Lack of good quality quartz	Treated / washed pot scrap works well. Potential to use in high quality Si or quartz solution
Marketing/branding of recycled silicon → <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usually: 10 years to integrate a new material and 10 years to introduce a new technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The process can be sold to implement it directly (e.g. in the USA) • Several Unique selling points: including recycled, environmentally friendly (better

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three different products are obtained from the pilots of the project • New material's comparison with virgin materials 	<p>LCA), «slave-free » production, and specific purity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care should be taken to ensure that each pilot does not cannibalize each other's markets and that the differences (process or final product) should be highlighted. • Brand name to identify this new Si (for example, Green Si? Re-Silicon?) for each of the products from the different pilots from the project should be determined. A recycling product is kind of a "new product".
<p>Selling secondary raw materials</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon tax for companies: the footprint of the technology of the project → good opportunity for secondary raw materials • 20 years ago, Silicon crisis. At this time, all sources were studied. It might occur in the future. Also, shortage of quartz in 10 years
<p>Si purity might not be achieved for PV</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find new target markets

2.5 Retrospective discussions about the project

In a final phase of the workshop, the participants carried out a retrospective review of the project. They responded to the questions posed by the visualisation of a hot air balloon retrospective tool and filled-in their responses (see Figure 8). Although additional time was provided for questions or comments, there was not enough time to discuss the sticky notes written by the participants. At the end of the online workshop, Roksana Rotter and Martin Bellmann extended farewells to all and expressed gratitude for their involvement. They also indicated that the results of this online stakeholder's workshop on secondary raw materials will be available to everyone through this report.

The Hot Air Balloon Retrospective

Figure 8: The Hot Air Balloon Retrospective

The following were the texts written on the sticky notes:

What added value does this project create?

For you as participant:

- knowledge on end applications
- could work on basics for EoL graphite recycling
- Learning more about the lifecycle and recycle values of silicon

For Europe:

- CBAM/carbon taxes
- Joint marketing
- New markets to develop
- Many results can be transferred to the semiconductor value chain. With potentially better outlook in Europe.

What are supportive elements moving the project forward?

- Politics
- Quartz market squeeze
- CBAM/carbon taxes
- Zero waste concepts

What are hindered elements/obstacles for the project?

- Status of solar industry in Europe
- Politics
- Long term silicon quartz availability

3 CONCLUSION

Thanks to this ICARUS workshop, we were able to discuss and collect key issues on the topics of target markets for secondary raw materials and obstacles in the project's supply chain. The perspectives offered by the external participants and the consortium, as well as the internal exchange within the consortium, were beneficial. The results of this workshop will be used as the basis for the second workshop in 6 months time, where we will build on them and go into more details.

4 APPENDIX

Agenda

date: 17. October
 time: 9:00 – 12:00
 place: online, via. Zoom

When?	What?	Who ?	How?
8:45	Meeting time before the workshop	sintef; chemcon, benkei, bifa	Same Zoom-link
9:00 – 9:05	Introduction to the workshop, aim of the workshop, agenda	Bifa (Roksana Rotter)	ppt
9:05 – 9:30	welcome Presentation of the project (15min) Presentation of the pilots (2-3min per pilot; in total 10min)	SINTEF (Martin Bellmann)	ppt
9:30 – 9:40	Presentation: introduction to target markets (10min)	Chemconserve (Marco Pieterse)	ppt
9:40 – 9:45	Introduction to group-work in Miro: Instruction for Miro from now: voice recording (for evaluation) group division into three groups (Breakout rooms)	Bifa (Roksana Rotter) Organisation Breakout Rooms: Monika Bokelmann	Ppt Breakout rooms: Silica, Hydrogen, Silicon until 10:40
9:45 – 10:40	Group work on target markets (3 groups, 55min) Sharing Miro Link and change to Miro (5min) Hint: zoom out to 5% in Miro Start voice-recording (Moderation) Step 1: individual work Voting: What are the possible markets for the secondary raw materials Silicon (Si), (Graphite), Silica and Hydrogen? Step 2: presentation + discussion presentation of the voting results Are there any missing target markets which should be added? What are the markets with the highest potential What are specific markets with specific product/technology, concrete company and contact Step 3 Individual work: SWOT analysis in terms of reaching target markets for secondary Silica/Hydrogen/Silicon.	Group 1: Silica Moderation: Ruth Berkmüller Support: Martin Bellmann, Rene Peche	Link Miro Group 1
		Group 2: Hydrogen Moderation: Monika Bokelmann Support: Matthias Seitz, Philippe Lenain, Wolfram P.	Link Miro Group 2
		Group 3: Silicon (Si) Moderation: Roksana Rotter Support: Marco Pieterse, Grégoire Rebeyre	Link Miro Group 3

	Step 4 discussion: for each target markets, sharing the participants thoughts		
10:40 – 10:45	Hint to break-out rooms and announcement of the break	Moderation: Bifa (Roksana Rotter) Organisation Breakout Rooms: Monika Bokelmann	Breakout Sessions (pilots: ROSI, RESITEC, LUX, NORTHERNSILICON; free move into breakouts; until 11:00)
10:45 – 11:00	Break with gallery: Every project member has the possibility to present a poster of the own task; every participant can move freely between the break out rooms and ask questions	Each partner is responsible for the own poster	Break Out Rooms for each pilot
11:00 – 11:05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome back Next steps Sharing link to Miro 	Moderation: Bifa (Roksana Rotter)	
11:00 – 11:30	Plenary work (30min): supply chain Explanation of the supply chain (5min) Step 1 Are the any adjustments to the supply chain? Step 2 What works well within each supply chain? ✓ What are challenges/potentials within the supply chain? ⚡ Are there any problems to obtain raw and auxiliary materials? Is there enough material available for the pilots? Step 3 Going through the red sticky notes: What would be possible approaches to solving these challenges/potential challenges?	Explanation Supply Chain + Expertise: SINTEF (Martin Bellmann) Moderation: bifa (Roksana Rotter) Notes taker: BENKEI, bifa	Miro board
11:30 – 11:55	Plenary work (25min) Find Miro board Reflection after the workshop with the visualisation of a hot air balloon. Step 1 Write down your thoughts Step 2 Discussion of the remaining questions What information would you need from the project?	Expertise benkei Moderation: Bifa (Roksana Rotter)	Same Miro board as before
11:55 – 12:00	Farewell, reference to the workshop in 6 months (April/May next year)	Bifa, SINTEF	plenary

Pilot A: Make the ingots manufacturing industry circular

Waste streams

- Silicon kerf generated from the diamond wire wafering of Cz-ingots in the photovoltaic industry constitutes a high volume silicon source with more than **300000 tons/year**
- ReSiTec has developed industrial processes for the recovery, purification and processing of silicon kerf into a dry, fine silicon powder material that could potentially be used as **anode material**
- Silica crucible waste materials and graphite waste materials have been treated in the pilot line specifically targeted for these waste streams

Pilot lines

Silicon kerf:

- Continuous drying of silicon kerf developed for higher capacities
- < 1 wt% moisture contents
- Industrial scale pre-treatment and post-treatment processes developed

Continuous drying equipment

Silicon kerf filter cake

Silicon kerf - deagglomerated

Silicon kerf - particles

Silica crucible and graphite waste materials:

Process flow sheet for pilot line developed for silica crucible and graphite waste materials

Rod mill for pilot line

Resulting powder material for production of SiC

Results

Silicon kerf:

ORIGINAL RESEARCH article

Front. Photonics, 22 February 2024
 Sec. Photovoltaic Materials and Devices
 Volume 5 - 2024 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphot.2024.1332830>

This article is part of the Research Topic
 Upgraded Metallurgical Grade (UMG) Silicon: Quality, Applications and
 Process Economics
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Silicon kerf loss as a potential anode material for lithium-ion batteries

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Specific capacities for the different material types as a function of cycle no.

- Silicon kerf processed by ReSitec has been compared to two commercial silicon nano materials for **Li-ion battery**

- Initial capacities, first cycle efficiencies and cycling stability **on par with references**

Silica crucible and graphite waste materials:

- Total impurities < 10 ppmw obtained for SiC produced from processed pot-scrap. **High purity silicon carbide achieved.**

- Testing ongoing on graphite for various applications

Conclusions

- Electrochemical testing of ReSiTec recycled silicon, show comparable results with commercial nano silicon - is a promising silicon source as anode material with competitive cost and beneficial carbon footprint
- High purity silicon carbide achieved from processed pot-scrap in pilot A (ReSiTec)

WP3—Recycling of Kerf and Other Waste streams From PV Production

Objective

Recover kerf/silicon, graphite, quartz from crucibles using Northern Silicon’s process technology to produce a silicon metal that can be re-used in solar panels

Challenges

1. PV panels used extremely high purity silicon— Northern Silicon’s process need to purify the waste to minimum 99.99999% Si
2. The kerf is doped with Phosphorous and Boron , 2 elements that are costly to remove but need to be reduced to less than 0,2ppm each

Kerf briquettes
Ready for processing

The induction furnace - removing impurities using 2 types of gases

Directional Solidification—last step in the NOSI process

Conclusions

- The NOSI Briquetting mix and technique works well for kerf and crucible quartz and is key to achieve energy efficient process
- Graphite from electrodes not reactive enough to replace carbon as reduction agent
- Silica from crucibles are well suited for production of standard silicon metal and may replace virgin material, but contains to many impurities to be a viable source in making high purity silicon metal
- Kerf very promising as raw material to make silicon wafers - Testing remains

WP4: Pilot C

Enabling industrial uptake-controlled conditionong of silicon

Objectives:

- Development of a pilot integrated line with a feeding system, a melting unit and a conditioning unit
- Integration of purification process for light element such as oxygen and carbon

Si-granules purity = 99,989% wt. (≈4N)

From 4N to 6N purity:

- Directional solidification to reduce metallics concertation
- Pilot line commissioned - proof of concept on 8kg ingot
- Minimum [metallics]: 5,5N to 6N due to [P]
- Silicon-ingot purity: *upcoming result*

Waste from Silicon Processing as a Source of Energy and Raw Materials

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Introduction

ICARUS aims to demonstrate modular processing solutions at industrial scale to retrieve 95% of high-value raw materials from silicon ingot and wafer manufacturing. Powder, dust or sludge are produced in many processes when processing silicon. In the ICARUS project, we try, among other things, to use these fines and the energy stored in them in a meaningful way. Waste containing silicon is omnipresent in the PV industry. That's why some research projects addressed the issue of Si-kerf recycling for the PV industry: SiKeLoR, Cabriss, SeLiSi and Eco-Solar, but none of these projects dealt with the use of energy. Alone the comparison of the standard formation enthalpies for CO₂ with -393.6 kJ/mol and SiO₂ with -911 kJ/mol shows the energetic potential that is in pure silicon – more than double

that for carbon. Until 2050 IEA forecasts additional installation of 4300 GW, which would correspond to a potential waste generation of 9.600.000 t silicon with an inherent market value of 86,67 Billion US\$ and implicit CO₂ emissions of 1156 Mt. As industrial partner of the H2020 project ICARUS we working on the upscaling of new innovating solutions to make Si-kerf a sustainable secondary raw material, but also we found new routes by the exploitation of synergies for optimal use of wafer and cell breakage coming from the PV industry. We show an example of recycling thought differently.

Technical Results

Sources of silicon waste

Very fine silicon usually comes from mechanical processing steps

1. Sawing processes (disk and/or band sawing processes)

2. Crushing large pieces of silicon to customer target size produces very fine silicon waste (dust)

conventional crushing with jaw breaker with target size 10 – 30 mm
Capacity: 100 t/m

contamination free, dust-free crushing with target size 5 – 35 mm
Capacity: 100 t/m

3. Sand Blasting of side cuts, tops and bottoms from c-Si ingots leads to very fine silicon waste

Our process leads to a mixture of fine silicon and corundum, which become a waste.

Silicon waste recycling – the idea

A simplified chemical equation which describes a silicon dissolution reaction can be written as follows:

The results were then transferred to other silicon-containing waste:

Motivation for alternative recycling route

- Material value
- Energy content

A comparison of the standard formation enthalpies for CO₂ with -393.6 kJ/mol and SiO₂ with -911 kJ/mol shows the energetic potential!

3. Purity

challenges:

- Particle size
- Surface
- Impurities

Grain size analysis of the filter dust generated during grinding

Grain size analysis of the fines from the grinding process:

Prüfzeitraum: 12.04.2024 - 20.04.2024

Na	<0,5 %	As	<0,1 %	Hf	<0,1 %
Nb	<0,5 %	Se	<0,1 %	Ta	<0,1 %
Al	<0,5 %	Br	<0,1 %	W	<0,1 %
Si	<0,5 %	Y	<0,1 %	Ra	<0,1 %
P	<0,2 %	Zr	<0,1 %	Fr	<0,1 %
S	0,3 %	Nb	<0,1 %	Ac	<0,1 %
Cl	<= 0,3 %	Mo	<0,1 %	Pt	<0,1 %
K	<0,3 %	Ru	<0,1 %	Au	<0,1 %
Ca	<0,1 %	Rh	<0,1 %	Pb	<0,1 %
Ti	<0,1 %	Pd	<0,1 %	Bi	<0,1 %
V	<0,1 %	Ag	98 %	Po	<0,1 %
Cr	<0,1 %	Gd	<0,1 %		
Mn	<0,1 %	In	<0,5 %		
Co	<0,1 %	Sn	<0,1 %		
Fe	<0,1 %	Sb	<0,1 %		
Ni	<0,1 %	Te	<0,1 %		
Du	<0,1 %	I	<0,1 %		
Zn	<0,1 %	Ba	<0,1 %		
Cu	<0,1 %	La	<0,1 %		
Ga	<0,1 %	Ce	<0,1 %		

Trockenverlust bei 105° C [1] 0,7 wt%
Glühverlust bei 900° C [1] 2,6 wt%

7 kg Cells : 155 g Ag

Conclusion:

Our motto **Si-waste to materials!** is very successful in implementation. A wide variety of Si waste could be completely converted into new products. The energy content of the silicon could be transferred to other products so that it can continue to be used.

Duration: June 2021 to May 2025

Budget: 11 M€

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